

Communication, dissemination and outreach activities

Project title: Plasma-Activated hydroGel: new frontiers in cardiac regenerative medicine

Project Number: 101067882

Project Acronym: PACGEL

Name of the fellow: Inès Hamouda

Name of the supervisor: Valeria Chiono

Host Institution: DIMEAS, Politecnico di Torino

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COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES TO GENERAL PUBLIC

	Communication channel	Target audience	Goal	Link
1	Social media accounts	Large public	Project presentation and awareness; update on events and advancement of the project	Instagram Facebook
2	Press release	Researchers and students	Highlight original and innovative project within MSCA fundings at the HI	Press release
3	Video	Large public; students and researchers	Project overall presentation to large public	MSCAnswers
4	European researcher Nights	Large public; citizens; adults and children	Science divulgation and introduction to the importance of science in daily life	UNIGHT
5	Just the Woman I am	Large public; citizens	Presentation of project and its impact on society	Just the women I am

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES (INCLUDING PUBLICATIONS AND CONFERENCES)

	Date	Type and format	Role	Target audience
1	19/04/2023	COST Action call presentation	Participant	Researchers from HI
2	09/05/2023	ERC-STG call presentation	Participant	Researchers from HI
3	17/05/2023	How to build a competitive CV for ERC grants - presentation	Participant	Researchers from HI
4	24/05/2023	Boost results in Horizon projects - presentation	Participant	Researchers from HI
5	10/06/2023 to 14/07/2023	Top Female Founder Summer School (TFFSS) - workshop	Short-listed to attend the workshop	European young female scientists in healthcare
6	4/09/2023 to 08/09/2023	European Society for Biomaterials (ESB) conference	Poster presentation	Scientific community
7	26/09/2023	Invited talk at Claude Bernard University - Lyon	Seminar presentation of research activities	Research group
8	02/10/2023 to 15/10/2023	Invited for internship at Le Mans University	Lab work and supervision of student	Student and research group

9	11/03/2024 – 20/03/2024	Coaching in pitching - Falling the Walls Context	Participant	MSCA Fellows
10	28/03/2024	ERC info days	Participant	Researchers from HI
11	18- 19/04/2025	Falling the Walls Lab Context	Participant – short-listed to pitch	MSCA Fellows and MSCA community
12	22/05/2024	How to design and write an ERC proposal part I - workshop	Participant	Researchers from HI
13	29/05/2024	How to design and write an ERC proposal part II - workshop	Participant	Researchers from HI
14	30/05/2024 to 01/06/2024	Summer Immersion on Innovative Approaches in Sciences - workshop	Selected to attend - participant	Scientists working on alternatives to animal models
15	20/06/2024	Starting a start-up: A success story from TFFSS	Invited talk	Young scientist women attending courses dealing with building a startup within healthcare system
16	25/06/2024 to 28/06/2024	Tissue Engineering and Regenerative Medicine International Society (TERMIS) Conference	Participant – poster presentation	Scientific community
17	19/07/2024	TFFSS workshop	Mentor	Young scientist women attending courses dealing with building a startup within healthcare system
18	12/09/2024	ERC work program workshop	Participant	Researchers from HI
19	21- 22/11/2024	Invited talk at Paul Sabatier University - Toulouse	Seminar presentation of research activities	Research group

Social media:

PACGEL is present in [Facebook](#) and [Instagram](#) as well as in X (previously Twitter) @msca_pacgel.

EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS:

PACGEL project generated experimental data results which will be exploited to submit manuscripts as scientific publication in high ranked peer reviewed journals.

In more details, the following manuscripts are under preparation:

- 1) **Draft title:** Plasma-activated biomaterials: new frontiers in curative and regenerative cardiac medicine; **Authors:** Inès Hamouda, Alice Zoso, Elena Marcello, Irene Carmagnola, Monica Boffito, Valeria Chiono; **Journal name:** Journal of Physics Materials; **Type of article:** review; **Brief description of the content:** The objective of this paper review is to report and illustrate the state-of-the-art of the recent atmospheric pressure plasma devices and techniques employed to activate polymers for cardiac tissue engineering applications. Through this review we consolidate the body of knowledge and offer a comprehensive review to assess the progress of plasma treatment of polymers and hydrogels toward new horizons of applications. **Planned submission date:** 30th of May 2025.
- 2) **Draft title:** ROS-scavenging chitosan hydrogels enhances antifibrotic activity: in vitro study; **Authors:** Inès Hamouda, Giuseppe Cutietta, Alice Zoso, Elena Marcello, Alexandra Montembault, Valeria Chiono; **Journal name:** Carbohydrate Polymers; **Type of article:** research paper. **Brief description of the content:** In this work, various chitosan hydrogels presenting different degree of acetylation (from 4 to 40%) were prepared and 2 crosslinking methods compared (using NaOH or NH₃) on the ROS scavenging ability. We found that chitosan hydrogel has excellent capacity to inhibit hydrogen peroxide generated from a cocktail of ROS derived from plasma jet linked with the increase of the degree of acetylation. Cell viability of human cardiac fibroblast cells wasn't affected; however, the presence of the chitosan hydrogel evidenced their protection toward fibrotic expression while in contact with various doses of oxidative stress conditions. **Planned submission date:** 30th of July 2025.
- 3) **Draft title:** Injectable and biodegradable plasma jet-activated PEO-based hydrogel for Plasma Medicine applications; **Authors:** Inès Hamouda, Alice Zoso, Elena Marcello, Emilie Choppé, Erwan Nicol, Valeria Chiono; **Journal name:** Frontiers in Biomaterial Science; **type of article:** research paper; **Brief description of the content:** In this work, an injectable and biodegradable PEO-based hydrogel was synthesized and investigated under atmospheric pressure plasma jet for bio-applications in Plasma Medicine. We report for the first time the quantification of long-lived ROS (hydrogen peroxide and nitrogen) within a PEO-based polymer and hydrogel. Short plasma jet treatment time of the polymer solution (up to 5 min) led to slightly affect the chemistry of the backbone (decrease of methacrylate signal in H¹NMR) without affecting rheological and mechanical properties of the hydrogel. Moreover, fast and efficient release of ROS is obtained within 24h. Additionally, the PEO-based hydrogel fully degrades within 30 days in presence of a lysozyme, making it promising for further clinical applications. **Planned submission date:** 30th of September 2025.

The publications derived results from the project will target scientific researchers in the field of biomaterials, tissue engineering and plasma medicine. The published results are expected to

provide additional data on the response of cardiac cells to controlled oxidative stresses and enhance fundamentals on the physicochemical properties of polymers and hydrogels in the presence of reactive oxygen species.

Furthermore, PACGEL results will pave the way towards a new research field exploiting plasma for cardiac regenerative medicine.

Planned future communication and dissemination activities

The following dissemination activities have been planned:

- **Oral presentation** at BIOINSIDE Laboratory Group Meeting at Politecnico di Torino, **date:** 16th of April, **title:** Plasma-activated hydrogel: new frontiers in regenerative medicine, **number of attendees:** 40.
- **Oral presentation** at SIMM Laboratory Monthly Seminar at ESPCI-Sorbonne University Paris, **date:** May 2025, **title:** Plasma-activated biomaterials for applied regenerative medicine, **expected attendees:** 60.

As underlined in the previous paragraphs **exploitations of results**, scientific publications will be submitted in 2025.

PACGEL results will be communicated to the general public by the supervisor, Prof. V. Chiono, during next communication events of her research groups such as the EU Researchers' Night in 2025 and Just the Woman I am 2026.